

**SPECIALIZES IN ORGANIZING ATHLETIC EXERCISE GROUPS
APPLICATION OF EXERCISES**

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Abstract. *In recent years, consistent measures have been taken in the republic to popularize physical education and sports, to promote a healthy lifestyle among the population, to create the necessary conditions for the physical rehabilitation of people with limited opportunities, and to ensure the country's proper participation in international sports arenas. Sports events and competitions are held in our country to ensure the physical and mental maturity of our future young generation. Organization of a healthy lifestyle of schoolchildren and students of higher educational institutions creates an opportunity for those interested in physical education and sports to contribute to the prosperity and development of our country in cooperation with all young people.*

Key words: *School students, physical rehabilitation, sports activities, children's sports, higher education.*

**СПЕЦИАЛИЗИРУЕТСЯ НА ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ СПОРТИВНЫХ ГРУЗОВ
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ УПРАЖНЕНИЙ**

Аннотация. *В последние годы в республике принимаются последовательные меры по популяризации физической культуры и спорта, пропаганде здорового образа жизни среди населения, созданию необходимых условий для физической реабилитации лиц с ограниченными возможностями, обеспечению должного участия страны на международных спортивных аренах. Спортивные мероприятия и соревнования проводятся в нашей стране для обеспечения физической и духовной зрелости нашего будущего молодого поколения. Организация здорового образа жизни школьников и студентов высших учебных заведений создает возможность для интересующихся физической культурой и спортом внести свой вклад в процветание и развитие нашей страны в сотрудничестве со всей молодежью.*

Ключевые слова: *Школьники, физическая реабилитация, спортивная деятельность, детский спорт, высшее образование.*

Relevance. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev 's Decree No. PF 5924 of January 24, 2020 on measures to further improve and popularize physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan, implementing specific programs that help to strengthen the health of the population in the field of physical education and sports, to attract young people to sports and to select talented athletes from among them, there is a need to form national teams with skilled athletes who provide high results in sports and create additional conditions for trainers. Identifying talented athletes and creating reserves for youth national teams by conducting

"Children's Sports Games" among sports school students-athletes under the Ministry of Physical Education and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan . in order to select young athletes and select talented athletes for big sports (selection), to establish a system of forming a sports reserve, to achieve high results in the popularization of sports among young people, based on the specific characteristics of the regions, the interest and wishes of the population, general education

schools, higher educational institutions, at least one priority, promising, developing, including national sports, and issues of selecting talented athletes are defined.

In order to ensure the implementation of this decree, it is certainly gratifying that many coaches working in the field of athletics are doing things worthy of their reputation in the system of training athletes. However, there are still specific shortcomings in the system of training athletes. Leading scientists have been carrying out a number of works on the organization of training processes in scientific institutions. Including selection of athletes for sports, participation in training, planning and management of training, F.A. Kerimov, O. V. Gancharova, V. N. Nikitushkin, M. N. Umarov, K.T. Shakirjonova, N.T. Tokhtaboev, M.S. Scientific research was carried out by Olimov and other scientists.

A clear example of this is the fact that Uzbek boys and girls are achieving positive results in world international competitions, Olympic and Paralympic games as a result of this upbringing.

Sports events and competitions are held in our country to ensure the physical and mental maturity of our future young generation. Organization of a healthy lifestyle of schoolchildren and students of higher educational institutions creates an opportunity for those interested in physical education and sports to contribute to the prosperity and development of our country in cooperation with all young people.

Physical education coaches and teachers have great responsibilities to raise the young generation to be physically fit and meet the requirements of the times. Therefore, a number of reforms are being carried out in the organization of physical education activities in the educational system. Expanding the range of theoretical and practical knowledge of physical education and sports among students of higher education institutions and secondary schools is an important issue. Organization of a healthy lifestyle, giving recommendations on independent exercise are among the activities that are very necessary now.

Physical exercises have a positive effect on the nervous and other various systems of the body, improve the spirit and competence of a person by strengthening his health.

The results of experiments conducted by many scientists show that the dynamics of physical formation and physical training of a person depend on the level of the student's ability to work and the nature and volume of regular exercises. Currently, although a lot of information has been collected on the effect of excessive physical load on the body of athletes, there are many cases of giving students the same loads without taking into account the characteristics of the body of young students. Due to this, it is necessary to properly plan the training process and to pay proper attention to the purposeful application of special exercises to the participants during the initial preparation period. Taking into account the above, it can be said that it is important to gradually use special exercises in training for all types of athletics.

The purpose of the work . *To achieve the development of physical qualities, taking into account age aspects in the organization of athletics training, using special exercises during training.*

Table 1

№	Tests	Experience guru x i				Control guru h i			
		T/O	T/K	differen ce __	%	T/O	T / K	differen ce __	%
1	Standing number 10 in the place during knee high __ yu guri sh (times)	7	5	2	14	7	6	1	11
2	10 meters in pairs _ _ sakra sh	7	5	2	14	7	6	1	11

3	30 meters p/s yu guri sh (sec)	5	4	1	11	5	4.5	0.5	8
4	20 square meters yu guri sh	4	3.15	0.85	9	4	4	0	0
5	80 m run	11	10	1	11	12	12	0	0

School shooters physical quality education and training structure define sh those who grow up if possible depending on, functional cases account take not in training special etc step by step from coaches big attention since sh as needed in experience provendi. Take it went from research that 's it found that light athletes Thai way in action or tida study and work the most floor volume common endurance tarbi ya la sh ga , in particular that 's right next to it special kill your friends separately attention is given This while of students physical qualities tarbi ya la sh da important Ahami ya tga have.

Summary: School students between talented and light to athletics either way yu qori Sort them out hot sh iga and physical to the Thai people looking y o' naltiri sh each one physical good from the teacher pulling until to the coaches to their own serious things on the side demand is enough.

Read the students young aspect account take not an occupation jara yo nini t ' ri plan sh live sh and those who grow up tool and styles through physical qualities tarbi ya la sh expected as a result gives In the experiment the students not to work in the Thai way special kill the others with together methodological instructions of all things features , its sh minds and tools t thief selectivity in practice proved .

REFERENCES

1. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022)
2. Шерали Хошимович Гофуров, Баходир Хошимович Гофуров ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА 5X5 ФУТБОЛ СПОРТ ТУРИНИ ОММАЛАШТИРИШ ОРҚАЛИ КЎРИШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИДА НУҚСОНИ БОР ШАХСЛАР ҲАРАКАТ ФАОЛЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zbekistonda-5x5-futbol-sport-turini-ommalashtirish-or-ali-k-rish-obiliyatida-nu-soni-bor-shahslar-arakat-faolligini-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022)
3. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Bahodir Hoshimovich G'Ofurov NOGIRONLAR ARAVACHASIDAN FOYDALANADIGAN UMURTQA POG'ONASI SHIKASTLANGAN YOSHLARNING ADAPTIV JISMONIY TARBIYASI // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/nogironlar-aravachasidan-foydalanadigan-umurtqa-pog-onasi-shikastlangan-yoshlarning-adaptiv-jismoniy-tarbiyasi> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022).
4. Миржамолов М.Х. ПАРА-СПОРТЧИЛАРНИНГ КИНЕМАТИК ҲАРАКАТ ИМКОНИАТЛАРИ ТАҲЛИЛИ // Fan-Sportga. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/para-sportchilarning-kinematik-arakat-imkoniyatlari-ta-lili> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022)
5. Шерали Хошимович Гофуров, Баходир Хошимович Гофуров ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА 5X5 ФУТБОЛ СПОРТ ТУРИНИ ОММАЛАШТИРИШ ОРҚАЛИ КЎРИШ

- ҚОБИЛИЯТИДА НУҚСОНИ БОР ШАХСЛАР ҲАРАКАТ ФАОЛЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zbekistonda-5x5-futbol-sport-turini-ommalashtirish-orali-k-rish-obiliyatida-nu-soni-bor-shahslar-arakat-faolligini-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022)
6. Sherali Xoshimovich G'Ofurov, Baxodir Xoshimovich G'Ofurov NOGIRONLAR ARAVACHASIDAN FOYDALANADIGAN UMURTQA POG'ONASI SHIKASTLANGAN YOSHLARNING ADAPTIV JISMONIY TARBIYASI // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/nogironlar-aravachasidan-foydalanadigan-umurtqa-pog-onasi-shikastlangan-yoshlarning-adaptiv-jismoniy-tarbiyasi> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022).
 7. 7.Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov MALAKALI SPINTERCHILARNING SPORT MASHG'ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/malakali-sprinterchilarning-sport-mashg-ulotlarini-rivojlantirishning-usullari> (дата обращения: 13.12.2022).
 8. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyrov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 13.12.2022).
 9. Sherali Hoshimovich G. Ofurov Qisqa masofaga yuguruvchi sportchilarni mashg'ulotlarini rivojlantirishning usullari //Scientific progress. – 2021. – №. 8.
 10. ЕОФУРОВ Ш. МАКТАБЛАРИДА БОШЛАНЕИЧ ТАЙЁРЛОВ ГУРУ^ ИДА ШУЕУЛЛАНУВЧИ ЕНГИЛ АТЛЕТИКАЧИЛАР МАСHEУЛОТЛАРИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ. – 2020.
 11. Sherali Hoshimovich G. O. MALAKALI SPINTERCHILARNING SPORT MASHG'ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – №. 4.
Mirjamolov, M. K., Mirjamolov, S. K., O'tashev, X. N., Arabov, X. S., & Odilov, R. F. (2022). MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH. MODERN SCIENCE, 2181, 3906.
 13. Faxriddinovich O. R. et al. METHODOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MOTION COORDINATION IN STUDENTS WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENTS O'zDJTSU //Scientific Impulse. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 436-445.
 14. Fakhridinovich O. R. et al. FUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE ORGANISM OF STUDENTS WITH DAMAGE TO THE MUSCULOSKELETAL SYSTEM //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – Т. 11. – №. 12. – С. 145-162.
 15. Миржамолов, М. Х., Одилов, Р. Ф., Валиева, Н. Ю., & Бахтиёров, Д. Б. (2022). Методика развития координации движений у студентов с нарушениями зрения. *Scientific progress*, 3(1), 549-556.